

STUDENTS' PERFORMANCE IN AN ONLINE AND FACE-TO-FACE LEARNING MODALITIES: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

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Students' Performance in an Online and Face-to-Face Learning Modalities: A Comparative Analysis

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Abstract

The study explores the usefulness of Fitness Health and Wellness at the University of the Visayas in implementation of the Hyflex learning. This study utilized the descriptive comparative research design. Anchored with the community of inquiry which will help the study of online learning and face to face learning Moreover, it has been recognized as having considerable potential to support higher order and deep learning through the interaction of social, cognitive, and teaching presences. All of these offer a useful structure to examine students' learning experience from the perspectives of collaboration, critical thinking, and knowledge construction. The lived experiences of the teachers have a greater impact on the lives of the students. Moreover, the results of the study reveals that there is a relationship in the different learning modalities the online learning and face-to-face learning in Physical Education Fitness Health and Wellness. This implies that the Hyflex Learning were implemented successfully through the unending support and cooperation among school administrators, teachers, students, and other stakeholders. However, it is a fact that students in online and face-to-face learning is highly recommended to reach out to the teacher if they have difficulties in performing the physical activities.

Keywords: *presence of the teacher, students' performance, hyflex learning, fitness health and wellness*

Introduction

Blended learning or hybrid learning or mixed-mode instruction, combines traditional classroom teaching with one or two other learning methods. Blended learning has become more common in recent years because of the development of data analysis and computation. Many educators have used the Learning Management System (LMS) to design their blended courses, which improved the students' learning outcomes and engagement levels. However, some researchers have pointed out the challenges of tracking students' learning activities and patterns in blended courses due to the complicated learning setting.

After defining the features of face-to-face and online learning, we learned the rules of how students behave in the three learning modes by examining the impact of various factors on their learning styles. This helped us to improve the educational resources and the curriculum design. Also, it is conducive to making an effective evaluation of learners and learning resources so as to promote students and improve learning effects (Jun et al., 2009).

As part of the curriculum, the Physical Education is one of the subjects that very crucial in online learning. This subject helps us to improve our physical and mental health. In this study it will help the students, teachers and school administration to conduct and improve the students' performance in physical education. The study is necessary to be conducted due to the fact that the physical activity improves interpersonal relationships in the classroom, as well as mental abilities like concentration and attention, all of which are crucial elements of better academic performance.

When the researcher taught Physical Education (PE) way back in 2021, He observed that students have difficulty with their studies in online learning, it is really too different from the classes in face-to-face learning specifically. However, we know that physical education is a performance-based subject. With this, students are struggling in their performances because they do not totally understand the instructions in online teaching, and also the instructors have a difficulty in teaching Physical Education because here in the Philippines, some instructors are more in performance or practical examinations. But nowadays, some of the instructors use different modalities, such as online learning, and face-to-face learning or in this school year, they call it Hyflex learning.

Physical activity is crucial for learning as well as for optimal development and growth of the students. In today's curriculum the health and wellness programs and its services are designed to encourage healthier lifestyles among students. The researcher found out series of gaps in teaching blending learning. The following are mentioned, namely; Skills gaps: students lack the practice needed to acquire necessary abilities. Motivation gaps: Students aren't driven to learn more or develop their talents. Environmental gaps: Lack of a learning atmosphere among students. Communication gaps: Communication problems occur among students.

The paper seeks to analyze some factors affecting students' performance in University of the Visayas both in the College of Arts and Sciences and College of Business Administrations who are enrolled in the course subject in Fitness, Health and Wellness.

For teaching the course subject in Fitness, Health and Wellness for 4 years in the university, most of the problems that exist was the difficulty of delivering the instructions in blended learning and the process itself on how the certain concepts are being tackled and performed. Tutorials and other sort of helping academically helped a lot in making learning possible. In this research, the researcher found out the factors that existed in the failure of the respondents in the course subject, not just failing but rather difficulty of the subject matter.

Moreover, this is valuable to the Physical Education instructors for it will serve as the basis in preparing a well-balanced program of

instruction and supervision. In addition, this will be a guiding factor in improving the teaching-learning process in the PE department. Hence, the result of this study would help the instructors adjust their teaching style on the effectiveness of either online or face-to-face classes based on the desired competencies and learning styles of the students. It will enable them to know the relatedness of the students' learning factors in Physical Education Performance.

In this study, this is a guiding tool that the Physical Education instructors have the opportunity to conduct more effectively in handling relevant Physical Education Courses. Hence, the researcher must find effective ways to teach Fitness health and wellness in physical education. To solve this problem, we need to undergo a survey from Fitness health and wellness respondents. However, the most effective way to deliver the subject matter is to have face-to-face sessions. This paper recommends a solution to solve the gap in the difficulty in teaching Fitness, Health and Wellness more effectively given the available learning modalities through conducting enhancement programs that allow the students to engage, apprehend, and participate physically. These enhancement programs may include webinars, online and blended physical exercises, and student physical performances.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study is to compare the students' performances in the different learning modalities the online learning and face-to-face learning and for the development of instructional materials for blended learning in Physical Education Fitness Health and Wellness at the University of the Visayas. Specifically, this study answered the following queries:

1. To what extent do the students manifest their level of the following constructs:
 - 1.1. teaching presence;
 - 1.2. social presence; and
 - 1.3. cognitive presence?
2. What are the students' performances in the Fitness Health and Wellness Subject during:
 - 2.1. online learning; and
 - 2.2. face to face learning?
3. Is there a significant difference in students' performance between online learning and face to face learning?
4. To what extent do the following factors influence the students' performance in online and face to face learning:
 - 4.1. teaching factors;
 - 4.2. social factors;
 - 4.3. student factors?
5. Based on the findings of the study, what instructional materials can be designed in the Hyflex blended learning?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive comparative design using an adapted questionnaire. The study looked into the characteristics of the participants during their online learning in terms of their interactions with the teachers, their relationship with their peers and how they are developing cognitively in a non-classroom setting. Comparative analysis was used to compare the students' performance in a physical education course when it was taught virtually or online and when it was taught face-to-face. In this study design, it was revealed which learning modality is more effective.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the college students who have completed the Fitness, Health, and Wellness subject coming from the two colleges in the university – the College of Business Administration and the College of Arts and Sciences.

Sample size and sampling. A quota sample of 150 students were considered as the participants of the study with equal allocation of 75 students per college (Table 1). To recruit the students, simple random sampling was used provided they were qualified as participants based on the criteria.

Table 1. *Distribution of the respondents by Department*

<i>College Departments</i>	<i>No. of Respondents</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
College of Business Administration (CBA)	75 students	50.0
College of Arts and Sciences (CAS)	75 students	50.0
Total	150 students	100.0

Inclusion Criteria. The participants were selected based on the following criteria:

- 1) they belong to either of the two colleges, regardless of gender; 2) they are 18 years old and above; 3) They have completed the subject Fitness Health and Wellness which was taught using two learning modalities; 4) they were willing to participate in the study and 5) they have signed the informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria. There are seven college departments that were not included to this study. These are the College of Criminal Justice,

College of Engineering Technology and Architecture, College of Education, College of Maritime Education, College of Allied Health Sciences and Gullas Law School.

Instruments

The main instrument used in this study is the standardized questionnaire for COI. The Community of Inquiry questionnaire is developed and validated by a collaborative research team in 2008. The members of the team, in alphabetical order, are Ben Arbaugh, Marti Cleveland-Innes, Sebastian Diaz, D. Randy Garrison, Phil Ice, Jennifer Richardson, Peter Shea and Karen Swan. Each student will be evaluated on the following scale parameters:

<i>Scale</i>	<i>Response</i>	<i>Ranges of Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
5	Strongly Agree	4.21-5.00	Very High
4	Agree	3.41-4.20	High
3	Somewhat Agree	2.61-3.40	Moderate
2	Disagree	1.81-2.60	Low
1	Strong Disagree	1.00-1.80	Very Low

As to reliability of the whole questionnaire, the Cronbach Alpha is 0.94 For the three constructs, the Cronbach alpha is; teacher presence is 0.91, Social presence is 0.91 and cognitive presence is 0.95.

The demographic profile is a fill-in questionnaire to solicit the data on age, and gender. In order to get the evaluation of the academic performance of the students, the researcher administered an examination during online and face-to-face modality to the same students.

Procedure

This part contains discussions of the data procedures for pre-data gathering, actual gathering, and post data gathering.

Pre – Data Gathering. In data gathering, the researcher underwent a series of procedures. The researcher complied with the comments and suggestions of the panelists during the design hearing. After receiving the comments and suggestions, the researcher asked for the Ethical Consideration of the study from the Research Ethics Committee

(*REC*). After obtaining all needed approval, the ethical considerations of the study were checked by the Research Ethics Committee and approved, and a Notice to Proceed (NTP) was given. After being given an NTP, the researcher submitted a letter to the Chief Academic Officer of the University of the Visayas and waited for approval. After the approval, the researcher went to the college dean to give the letter, and the study was conducted.

Actual Data Gathering. On the day of the data gathering, the researcher explained the purpose and mechanics of the survey so that the respondents would have an idea about it. The researcher asked the instructors about the scores of the students in online and face-to-face classes and pinpoint at least some of the reasons the research was conducted. Hence, the data on the performance evaluation of the respondents was taken through a standardized questionnaire, including the qualitative data coming from their instructors.

Post Data Gathering. The data gathered were collected, tallied, tabulated, and statistically treated. The data were encoded on a computer and protected by a password. Only authorized persons have access to the data. The data disposed, once the study is published in an accredited journal or after a year.

Data Analysis

With the data that was analyzed through statistical tools. For the student's status on the three domains of the community of inquiry and their performance in the course Fitness Health and Wellness, descriptive statistics were used, specifically the mean and standard deviation. To compare the students' performance in the physical education course, the t- test of an independent sample was applied. After the processing, interpretation, and analysis of data, the instructional plan was created. An instructional plan that was deepen the teaching skills of Physical Education Instructors by giving themselves a time to adjust their expertise to the students with the kind of learning modalities

Ethical Considerations

The service of the University of the Visayas Ethics Institutional Review Board was availed. The Institutional Review Board basically allowed third parties, not known to the researcher to check for ethical consideration anchored on Beneficence, Respect and Justice. Beneficence, Respect and Justice

In conducting research, ethical consideration was given importance to protect the validity, dignity, and safety of the research participants to strengthen its quality standards. Several ethical considerations were taken into account to ensure that the study was conducted in appropriate manner (Babbie & Mouton, 2001). In compliance with ethical considerations in conducting research to all participant's, written consent was provided to the participants who participated in the conduct of the online research study and secured accordingly and made sure that only those who are permitted to join the conduct of this study were included in the teaching learning process for this purpose.

Beneficence. The participants simply checked the items based on their thoughts and opinions in the prepared questionnaires. They were given thirty (30) minutes to answer and review their answer. Considerations were given as to the time and number of items. The researcher virtually shared or presented the questionnaires to the identified respondents to ensure safety and, on the process of gathering data, the researcher ensured the safety and harm of the respondents. The results of the study were an avenue for enhancing the curriculum and to contribute to the benefit of effective teachers and quality learning acquisition amid the pandemic.

Respect. The respondents in the study were of school age. Approved letters were provided and orientation was conducted. The researcher also emphasized that there was no force or coercion during the participation rather it was purely voluntary.

Justice. The participants in the study were the College students who were treated fairly and impartially. Moreover, privacy and utmost confidentiality of the respondents were given serious consideration and safety. For their integrity, respondents were not forced to answer or to give their answers and they were allowed to proceed to answer the next questions. Readiness of the respondents was considered in answering the questions and the researcher understood and respected their decision and set another schedule for the convenience of the respondents

Thus, the researcher virtually explained the purpose in conducting this research to the respondents and asked for their honest answers to ensure the success of the study. Respondents were informed ahead of time. All participants used the same questionnaires. Their participation was their generous contribution to the success of the study. Appreciation through words of thanks as driving force for accomplishing the questionnaire was extended by the researcher to the respondents.

Finally, with all the guidelines prescribed by the University, all requirements were fully accomplished before the conduct of the study. Ethical review and approval by the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of the University Ethics Committee was sought. Thus, the principles and standards of the Belmont Report supported the conduct of this study.

Protection of Human Rights.

Participation in this study did not violated the human rights of the respondents or participants thus, safeguarding their integrity to protect their personal identity.

The researcher allowed the Institutional Review Board (IRB) to check and review the manuscript before the conduct of the study to assure its validity based on the prescribed guidelines.

Risk-Benefit Assessment

Risk-Benefit Ratio Determination

The researcher used codes to represent the respondents' profile. The researcher assured the respondents that their responses were handled with strict confidentiality and for study purposes only. The cooperation of the respondents was important for the success of gathering the data. The researcher explained the importance of the respondents' participation especially in answering the questionnaire. The respondents' honest responses to the questionnaire certainly helped in attaining the objectives of the study. Thus, the respondents were given ample time to review the answered items to ensure that the questionnaire was answered completely. The data collected were kept properly with confidentiality.

If in any case, the participants were not available on the stipulated time of the online conduct of the study, they were allowed to email the questionnaire to the researcher at their convenience.

In the conduct of the study, the researcher assured that the information provided by the participants were also beneficial to those who might experience the same dilemma. The responses stated in full detail with points of reflection to the advantage of the readers, the university and future studies.

Content, Comprehension and Documentation

Informed consent forms indicating the approval of the Institutional Review Board (IRB) were given to the participants for their participation in the study. Participation of the

College students were solely voluntary. Signing in the form or agreement was verified and provisions in the agreement were included in the consent form. Clear and comprehensive provisions were stipulate and made sure that the participants understood the consent. Accommodated clarifications or further inquiries to the provisions in the consent form was attended.

Participant Status. Orientation of the respondents on the conduct of the study was more of research rather than treatment. The study focused only on the performance as college students as basis to determine the effectiveness of the Hyflex Learning in obtaining quality learning acquisition with no treatment of whatsoever applied on them. The data collected were used for research purposes only.

Study goals. The researcher presented and discussed the objectives of the study to the respondents. The goal of the study was to determine the performance of the students in online and face to face learning. Likewise, the study determined the importance of the teaching strategies that make the online and face to face learning more effective. The output or results of the study served as basis for enhancing the performance of college students in Physical Education.

Type of data. Prior to the conduct of this study, the researcher oriented the respondents on the type of data to be collected. Quantitative data were generated from the questionnaire based on the respondents' responses and accumulated score.

Procedures. The researcher secured the approval of the respondents through the informed consent form of the students and the data gathered were collected, tallied, and tabulated and statistically treated using weighted mean and get the complete enumeration of the academic performance.

Nature of Commitment. The researcher demonstrated this research undertaking through honest conduct by following correct and appropriate research procedures and methods. The researcher personally spent time and met the University Academic Chief Officer, College Deans of two Department, and teachers to ask permission and to be informed of the availability of the respondents before the conduct of the study.

The respondents were given thirty-four (34) items questions to be accomplished in thirty (30) minutes to answer the questionnaire. Having to travel during the conduct of this study, the researcher took serious efforts and observed minimum health protocols to complete this undertaking with patience and commitment on his part to contribute valuable information to the body of research.

Sponsorship/Funding. This study was in compliance to an academic requirement for Masteral Degree and all the expenses and necessities incurred were shouldered by Commission on Higher Education scholarship named SCHOLARSHIPS FOR INSTRUCTORS' KNOWLEDGE ADVANCEMENT PROGRAM (SIKAP).

Selection of Participant. This study employed complete enumeration. Specifically, one hundred fifty college students of University of the Visayas were expected to participate in the study.

Likewise, the selection of respondents conformed to the inclusion criteria set by the researcher with the Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval.

Potential Risks. The respondents informed of the merits of their honest answer to the questions and assured the confidentiality of information. In case of physical discomfort to questions needed delicate answers from the respondents, the researcher assured that these would not be divulged or shared to anybody else and the result purposely be used solely for research. This avoided inconvenience or do away with stress among the participants.

Potential Benefit. This study was beneficial to the College Students to improve their academic performance in online and face to face learning. Feedbacks of their level of academic learning were essentially used to guide the teachers of enhancing and looking for the necessary interventions and strategies to increase learning acquisition of the students. Likewise, the result of this study served as basis for research to increase academic performance of College Students as well as for curriculum enhancement program to ensure the efficient delivery of quality instruction.

Alternatives. The researcher informed the respondents of the given schedule to when they would answer the questionnaire. In case of the unavailability of the respondents in the scheduled time, the researcher set a schedule for a virtual follow up to meet the participants to comply with the required data to make the study possible.

Incentives / Compensation. There was no monetary compensation given to the participants. However, only words of gratitude expressed by the researcher to the respondents in helping and participating in the conduct of the study. Moreover, they received tokens as symbols of the researcher's gratitude for the precious time shared during the conduct of the study.

Confidentiality Pledge. To protect the privacy of the college students, cooperating teachers, and supervisors, writing the respondents' name in the questionnaire was not indicated. However, codes were used to attest the respondents' privacy and confidentiality. The questionnaires were kept by the researcher and the answers were secured and would not be divulged to safeguard the respondents' confidentiality.

Voluntary Consent. Participation of the respondents to answer and accomplish the research questionnaire was encouraged for only one questionnaire as well as the learning activities in the delivery of the lessons and clarified or considered as non- academic requirement. On the other hand, their participation was strictly voluntary and that failure to volunteer would never result in any penalty or loss of benefit.

Right to Withdraw and Withhold Information. The respondents were informed of their right to withdraw or withhold any specific information. They were also encouraged that their participation and the beneficially of their responses enhanced the development of the education sector and academe.

Informed Consent/ Implied Consent/ Process Consent/ Assent

To safeguard the rights of the respondents of this study, the researcher gave an informed consent form indicating the approval of IRB and distributed to the respondents along with the discussion of the nature of the research study. The participation of the respondents in the research study was purely and entirely voluntary and agreement to the said research was validated by each informant's signature in the consent form.

Confidentiality Procedures.

Privacy and Confidentiality. Confidentiality of the participants was strictly maintained to ensure privacy of the information given. The disclosure of the participant's identity was based on the participant's permission. No identity was exhibited. Pseudonyms were used, no pictures were taken and the subjects' academic records were kept confidentially and were not disclosed. With that, a certification of confidentiality was available in the study.

Privacy and Confidentiality

To protect the rights to privacy and confidentiality of the participants, the researcher did not force them to include details which they thought violated their privacy. Moreover, they used pseudonyms if they wanted to and their physical looks have been not exposed to make sure and guarantee confidentiality and privacy of their identity. All information and data were kept private and safe from any disclosure or to whatsoever that may compromise their identity.

Debriefing, Communications, and Referrals.

This human research debriefing referred to a conversation between the researchers and the respondents that happened after the research undertakings and this also refers to the questioning of the respondents or instructing at the end of the mission. It was also the position sitting counterpart of the knowledgeable approval as well as being there to perform in a method so as the respondents would benefit feel respected. The researcher made sure to have respect by carefully attending with reactions of the respondents of the survey and/or other personnel are being involved in the research study.

Conflict of Interest

Although the researcher was a faculty member of the school being studied, he had no direct subjects taught to the respondents. Likewise, the researcher was not affiliated with where some respondents were taken. Therefore, the respondents were influenced by the researcher to participate in this study. On the other hand, the researcher emphasized the importance of the study to enhance and improve performance and learning acquisition of the College Students for their future career and not for any personal interest. The researcher's commitment to follow properly the scientific method of conducting the research safeguarded to eliminate or reduce biases. A proper citation of information sources appropriately instigated by the researcher. Data procedures, analyses and ethical consideration were employed and applied to assure the validity and reliability of the study.

Moreover, this study was financed by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) and was not a collaborative endeavor in nature. Thus, the researcher, being the author, held the intellectual property rights, as well as the publication rights and responsibility of sharing information. In this study, a statement of agreement between the Principal Investigator (PI) and research adviser was made stipulating the adviser as secondary author in any or all publications of this study. Reproduction of this paper was allowed with the consent of the principal investigator.

Finally, this study was conducted after the approval of Institutional Review Board (IRB). The selection of the respondents from University of the Visayas where the researcher conducted the study and the inclusion and exclusion criteria set contributed to the authenticity of the study. For these reasons, conflicts of interest and biases were prevented to occur.

Collaborative Study Terms of Reference

In case this study be published, the researcher served as the primary author of the study, while the adviser would be the secondary author. The school and the division with which the researcher was affiliated may also use the published study in school and division evaluation.

Moreover, the results were disseminated by partner schools where the study was conducted. For monetary incentives, in case there is, both the researcher and adviser benefit to enjoy the privilege thereof. This arrangement was made into knowledge and agreement between the researcher and the adviser. However, should there be any interested person, group or entity who would claim whatever credit or advantage this study might bring to them, written or any form of permission or authority must be duly awarded or given to them for whatever purpose it may serve them best.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the analyzes and interprets the data obtained from the evaluation of the Students Performance in an Online and Face-to-Face Learning Modalities: A Comparative Analysis.

Community of Inquiry

The Community of Inquiry model was developed from a study by Garrison, Anderson, and Archer that was conducted in 2001. The model of a community of inquiry consisted of three key elements of an educational experience: teaching presence, cognitive presence, and social presence. This study determined the educational experience of the students during their physical education class. Table 2 presents the results of the survey on teaching presence. The items assess various aspects of the instructor's engagement and effectiveness in fostering a collaborative and supportive learning environment

Clear Communication was measured in items one to four (means are 4.14, 4.24, 4.30, and 4.25) of which the students strongly agree. Teachers play a crucial role in creating a positive learning experience. Outstanding results may be attributed to instructors who consistently communicated important course topics, goals, instructions, and due dates. Clear communication ensures that students are well-informed, reducing confusion and promoting a focused learning environment.

Table 2. *Teaching presence of Fitness Health and Well Being*

Community Inquiry Indicators	Mean	SD	Desc.
A. Teaching Presence			
The instructor clearly communicated important course topics.	4.14	1.0512	Agree
The instructor clearly communicated important course goals.	4.24	0.8944	Strongly Agree
The instructor provided clear instructions on how to participate in course learning activities.	4.30	0.9092	Strongly Agree
The instructor clearly communicated important due dates/time frames for learning activities.	4.25	0.9242	Strongly Agree
The instructor was helpful in identifying areas of agreement and disagreement on course topics that helped me to learn.	4.19	0.9336	Agree
The instructor was helpful in guiding the class towards understanding course topics in a way that helped me clarify my thinking.	4.28	0.9331	Strongly Agree
The instructor helped to keep course participants engaged and participating in productive dialogue.	4.18	0.9308	Agree
The instructor helped to focus discussion on relevant issues in a way that helped me to learn.	4.17	0.9339	Agree
The instructor encouraged course participants to explore new concepts in this course.	4.21	0.9389	Strongly Agree
Instructor actions reinforced the development of a sense of community among course participants.	4.23	0.8635	Strongly Agree
The instructor helped to focus discussion on relevant issues in a way that helped me to learn.	4.23	0.9171	Strongly Agree
The instructor provided feedback that helped me understand my strengths and weaknesses relative to the course's goals and objectives.	4.19	0.9336	Agree
The instructor provided feedback in a time fashion	4.17	0.9339	Agree
Factor mean	4.21	0.9321	Outstanding

N= 150; Ranges for Means: 4.21 – 5.00= Strongly Agree (SA) /Outstanding; 3.41 – 4.20= Agree/Very Satisfactory; 2.61 – 3.40=Somewhat agree/Satisfactory; 1.81 – 2.60= Disagree/Fair; 1.00 - 1.80= Strong Disagree (SD)/Poor

The next five items measure the guidance and facilitation skills of the teacher which the students either agree or strongly agree. The outstanding results might indicate that instructors were effective in guiding class discussions, helping students understand course topics, and encouraging productive dialogue. This suggests that the instructors facilitated a learning environment where students felt supported in their exploration of new concepts and the clarification of their thoughts. Generally, the teachers encourage students to explore. Instructors who encourage students to explore new concepts contribute to a dynamic and intellectually stimulating learning environment. The outstanding results may indicate that teachers fostered a culture of curiosity and exploration, motivating students to delve deeper into the subject matter. Focusing discussions on relevant issues is a key aspect of effective teaching. Outstanding results may indicate that instructors skillfully guided discussions, ensuring that they were pertinent to the course topics and conducive to student learning.

Community Building was also encouraged by the teacher (items 10 and 11) Teachers who reinforce the development of a sense of community among course participants contribute to a positive learning atmosphere. This community-building aspect is crucial for collaborative learning, as students feel connected to their peers and the instructor, fostering a supportive learning environment. The last two items were agreed by the students about feedback and assessment. Effective feedback is a key component of the teaching and learning process. Outstanding results may suggest that instructors provided constructive feedback that helped students understand their strengths and weaknesses in relation to the course goals and objectives. Timely feedback is particularly important for students' continuous improvement. Timely feedback is critical for students to adjust and improvements in their learning journey. The outstanding

results related to the promptness of feedback suggest that instructors were responsive to students' needs and provided timely guidance for their academic progress.

In summary, the outstanding results in the teachers' presence in the community of inquiry, suggest that the instructors were effective in communication, guidance, community building, feedback provision, and encouraging an exploratory mindset among students. These positive outcomes contribute to a rich and supportive learning environment that enhances students' overall learning experiences.

Social Presence of the Students

Another element of the community of inquiry was the social presence of the students. The social presence of the students in the community of inquiry was rated very satisfactory (mean=3.98). This positive assessment suggests that the students experienced a strong sense of belonging, comfort, and interaction in the online learning environment.

The positive rating in "Getting to know other course participants gave me a sense of belonging in the course" indicates that students felt connected to the learning community. This sense of belonging is crucial for creating a supportive and inclusive online environment. The ability to form distinct impressions of other course participants suggests that students actively engaged with their peers. This could contribute to a richer social experience, where students recognize and appreciate the diversity of perspectives within the online community.

Table 3. *Social Presence of the Students*

Social Presence Indicators	Mean	SD	Desc.
Getting to know other course participants gave me a sense of belonging in the course	4.14	0.96	Agree
I was able to form distinct impressions of some course participants.	4.02	0.9485	Agree
Online or web-based communication is an excellent medium for social interaction.	4.03	0.9123	Agree
I felt comfortable conversing through the online medium.	3.94	0.9064	Agree
I felt comfortable participating in the course discussions.	3.92	1.0048	Agree
I felt comfortable interacting with other course participants.	4.10	0.9522	Agree
I felt comfortable disagreeing with other course participants while still maintaining a sense of trust.	4.03	0.9826	Agree
I felt that my point of view was acknowledged by other course participants.	3.67	1.0672	Agree
Online discussions help me to develop a sense of collaboration.	3.99	0.9617	Agree
Factor Mean	3.98	0.9759	Very Satisfactory

N = 150; Ranges for Means: 4.21 – 5.00 = Strongly Agree (SA) / Outstanding; 3.41 – 4.20 = Agree / Very Satisfactory; 2.61 – 3.40 = Somewhat agree / Satisfactory; 1.81 – 2.60 = Disagree / Fair; 1.00 – 1.80 = Strong Disagree (SD) / Poor

The recognition of online or web-based communication as an excellent medium for social interaction highlights the effectiveness of the chosen platform. This positive perception is key to fostering meaningful connections and collaborative learning experiences. The students' comfort in conversing through the online medium and participating in course discussions indicates that the online platform was conducive to open communication. Feeling at ease in the virtual space is essential for building a strong social presence.

The comfort level in disagreeing with other course participants while maintaining a sense of trust is a noteworthy aspect. This suggests that the online community cultivated an environment where diverse opinions were respected, contributing to a healthy exchange of ideas. The perception that one's point of view was acknowledged by other course participants is a positive indicator of effective communication and respect within the online community. This acknowledgment contributes to a sense of validation and engagement. The recognition that online discussions help in developing a sense of collaboration indicates that students see the value of interactive and collaborative learning. This fosters teamwork and mutual support among students in the online space.

In conclusion, the very satisfactory rating in the social presence of students within the community of inquiry reflects a positive and inclusive online learning environment. Students not only felt a sense of belonging but also expressed comfort, trust, and active participation in the virtual community. These outcomes are crucial for creating an effective and engaging online learning experience that promotes both academic and social growth.

Cognitive Presence of the Students

Cognitive presence of the students during online classes was determined using a questionnaire. The result of the survey is presented in Table 4. The very satisfactory rating (mean=4.08) in cognitive presence within the community of inquiry indicates that students

experienced a robust and effective engagement with the course content.

Table 4. *Cognitive Presence of the Students*

COGNITIVE PRESENCE	Mean	SD	Desc.
Problems posed increased my interest in course issues.	3.91	1	Agree
Course activities piqued my curiosity.	3.97	0.875	Agree
I felt motivated to explore content related questions.	4.05	0.9561	Agree
I utilized a variety of information sources to explore problems posed in this course	4.12	0.8961	Agree
Brainstorming and finding relevant information helped me resolve content related questions.	4.12	0.9145	Agree
Online discussions were valuable in helping me appreciate different perspectives.	4.16	0.9398	Agree
Combining new information helped me answer questions raised in course activities.	3.90	1.0677	Agree
Learning activities helped me construct explanations/solutions.	4.10	0.9074	Agree
Reflection on course content and discussions helped me understand fundamental concepts in this class.	4.13	0.936	Agree
I can describe ways to test and apply the knowledge created in this course.	4.21	0.921	Agree
I have developed solutions to course problems that can be applied in practice.	4.11	0.9201	Agree
I can apply the knowledge created in this course to my work or other non-class related activities.	4.14	0.9156	Agree
Factor mean	4.08	0.9435	Very Satisfactory

N = 150; Ranges for Means: 4.21 – 5.00 = Strongly Agree (SA) / Outstanding; 3.41 – 4.20 = Agree / Very Satisfactory; 2.61 – 3.40 = Somewhat agree / Satisfactory; 1.81 – 2.60 = Disagree / Fair; 1.00 – 1.80 = Strong Disagree (SD) / Poor

The acknowledgment that problems posed increased interest in course issues suggests that the course content was engaging and relevant. The students' motivation to explore content-related questions indicates a proactive and curious approach to learning. The use of a variety of information sources to explore problems demonstrates a depth of engagement. Students actively sought information from diverse perspectives, indicating a well-rounded and comprehensive approach to problem-solving.

The positive responses related to brainstorming, finding relevant information, and combining new information for problem resolution indicate effective problem-solving strategies. This suggests that students not only engaged with course content but also applied critical thinking skills. The recognition that online discussions were valuable in appreciating different perspectives highlights the importance of collaborative learning. This positive perception suggests that discussions were effective in fostering a community of learners who could share diverse viewpoints.

Affirmative responses to learning activities helping in constructing explanations or solutions indicate a successful learning process. Students were able to actively contribute to the generation of knowledge and solutions. The acknowledgment that reflection on course content and discussions helped in understanding fundamental concepts suggests a metacognitive approach to learning. Reflection is a key element in deepening understanding and connecting concepts. The ability to describe ways to test and apply the knowledge created in the course, as well as developing solutions that can be applied in practice, indicates a transfer of knowledge from the classroom to real-world scenarios. This application-focused approach aligns with practical learning outcomes.

The recognition that the knowledge created in the course can be applied to work or other non-class-related activities signifies a practical and applicable dimension to the learning experience. This suggests a real-world relevance to the course content.

In summary, the very satisfactory rating in cognitive presence implies that the course effectively facilitated a rich and active learning environment. Students demonstrated not only an increased interest in the course content but also a high level of motivation, critical thinking, collaborative learning, and the ability to apply knowledge in practical scenarios. These positive outcomes indicate a successful

implementation of cognitive presence in the community of inquiry, contributing to a meaningful and transformative learning experience.

Table 4 shows the cognitive presence of the Fitness Health and Wellness. The items in the data were collected from the respondents reflected that the academic performance of the subject. It shows that the respondents agree to the academic contents learned from the instructors in the hyflex learning. The hyflex learning could be the reason of getting a good academic performance of the students because they could perform either online or face to face situation. They don't have a learning problem or controversies in the subject since they can perform the activities in a moderate manner. Hence, the hyflex learning does not give us a hard time in order to learn the subject matter but rather it allows us to exert more pertaining to the performances given by the instructor either as a group or individual.

Difference in the Students' Performance Between those in the Online Learning and Face-to-face

The data of the Fitness Health and Wellness included in this study are the scores of the final examinations of the respondents in Online and Face – to – Face mode of instruction. The result of the survey and the difference between the online and face-to-face learning is shown in Table 5.

The mean score for the "Online Class" group is 99.43, while the mean score for the "Face-to-face Class" group is 99.98. These values represent the average scores achieved by students in each group which is very high or almost perfect. High scores in both the online and face-to-face classes suggest that the instructional strategies employed in both settings were effective. This could include clear communication, engaging teaching methods, and well-designed assessments. The high scores may reflect the quality of learning materials provided in both formats. Whether online or face-to-face, the materials used for instruction, including textbooks, multimedia, and assignments, may have contributed to the students' understanding and success. Moreover, the high scores often indicate a high level of student engagement. Both online and face-to-face classes may have succeeded in fostering an environment where students were motivated to participate actively in the learning process and that instructors in both settings were able to communicate course content and expectations clearly. Instructors who can adapt their teaching methods to different formats, such as online and face-to-face, are essential. The high scores may imply that instructors were able to successfully adapt their strategies to meet the needs of students in both environments.

In the case of the online class, the high scores could indicate successful integration of technology into the learning process. This might include the use of online platforms, multimedia resources, and interactive tools that enhanced the learning experience. High scores may suggest that students were motivated and disciplined in managing their online learning experience. This reflects positively on both students' commitment and the design of the online course.

Assessments play a crucial role in gauging students' understanding of the material. The high scores suggest that the performance assessment, effectively measured students' grasp of the content.

Table 5. *Difference in Students Physical Education Performance Between Online and In Face-to- Face Classes*

Variable	Group	Mean score	SD	T value	P value	Remarks
Scores	Online Class	99.43	2.33	2.90*	.011	Significant Difference
	Face-to-face class	99.98	0.19			

Significant at . < 05

It was hypothesized that there was no significant difference in the performance of the students during the online classes and face-to-face classes.

The t-test of independent sample was used to test the hypothesis. The t-value is 2.90, and it is marked with an asterisk (*). The t-value is a measure of the difference between the means relative to the variation in the data. The asterisk indicates that this difference is statistically significant. The p-value associated with the t-value is 0.011. The p-value is a measure of the probability that the observed differences occurred by chance. In this case, a p-value of 0.011 is less than the typical significance level of 0.05, indicating statistical significance.

The table concludes that there is a "Significant Difference" between the scores of the "Online Class" and "Face-to-face Class" groups based on the statistical analysis. The statement "Significant at . < 05" reinforces that the observed difference is statistically significant at the 0.05 significance level. In other words, there is less than a 5% chance that the observed difference occurred by random chance.

In summary, the table suggests that there is a statistically significant difference in scores between the online class and face-to-face class groups. The t-test indicates that this difference is unlikely to have occurred by random chance, and the observed difference is deemed

statistically meaningful. Students in one of the face-to-face performed significantly higher than the online format in terms of scores. This means that the difference of 0.45, even how small, has significance in the comparison analysis.

The study revealed that students have better performance during the face-to-face classes than the online sessions. This may imply that students may have a preference for face-to-face learning environments, finding them more conducive to their learning style. This could be influenced by factors such as the immediacy of interaction, in-person discussions, and the physical presence of an instructor. In-Person Engagement: often provide immediate, real-time engagement with instructors and peers. If this type of interaction is more effective for certain learning outcomes, the higher performance in face-to-face classes may indicate the importance of interpersonal communication and interaction in the learning process. Physical education classes may require hands-on activities, or practical demonstrations that are better facilitated in a face-to-face setting. If the online format lacks the ability to effectively replicate these hands-on experiences, it could contribute to lower performance.

In addition, face-to-face classes may provide better access to physical resources, and equipment, which can enhance the learning experience. Online classes may present technical challenges, such as internet connectivity issues, access to required software, or device compatibility. If students face obstacles in navigating the online learning platform, it could affect their performance. If students lack digital literacy skills or familiarity with online learning platforms, they may face challenges in navigating the virtual environment. In contrast, face-to-face classes may require less reliance on technology and digital literacy.

Collaborative learning and group activities are often integral to the learning process. Face-to-face classes may offer more natural opportunities for interaction and collaboration among students, contributing to better performance in activities that require teamwork. Face-to-face classes may allow for more immediate and individualized attention from instructors. Students who benefit from personalized feedback and guidance may perform better in a face-to-face setting.

It is crucial to conduct a thorough analysis, to understand the specific factors influencing the performance difference between face-to-face and online classes.

Additionally, addressing challenges and optimizing the design of online courses can help bridge the gap and enhance the effectiveness of online learning experiences.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the data gathered and analyzed, the researcher concludes that both learning modalities the online learning and face-to-face learning in Physical Education Fitness Health and Wellness can yield good performance. Thus, Hyflex Learning can be implemented successfully through the unending support and cooperation among school administrators, teachers, students, and other stakeholders. Thus, the evidence is growing rapidly of the importance of the theory of community of inquiry “as a significant determinant of student satisfaction, perceived learning, and sense of community” (Garrison & Arbaugh, 2007).

Based on the results of the study, the researcher makes recommendations on the aspects of the theory and principle, practice, and future research. To wit,

1. Teaching Strategies - The researcher recommends the strategies in handling the subject, particularly the college instructors, to evaluate their impact the implementation of the learning delivery modality and ensure that it is properly implemented. The community of which the school belongs should also be visited and school leaders should work hand-in-hand with them for evaluation purposes.
2. Policy makers recommendation - The researcher recommends that policy makers should be actively involved in the implementation of Hyflex Learning by creating policies that would help it efficient implementation. They could also create a policy wherein modules and learning materials are intended and evaluated by the different experts in the field and shall undergo rigorous editing and proofreading. They could also help by allocating more funds for the education sector.
3. Instructional Materials and Strategies – The researcher recommends the following:
 - a) The instructor will conduct a webinar to understand the goal of Hyflex Learning in Fitness Health and Wellness and be able to apply in the class.
 - b) The instructor will conduct a weekly assessment for the students in online delivery to determine the effectiveness of their performance.
 - c) Given the uploaded videos in the LMS, the instructor will make a checklist of the physical exercises in online delivery and the students will monitor in their own way.
 - d) The students will perform the physical performance in fitness health and wellness.
 - e) Then instructor will give the students instructions in online and the performance will be face-to-face.
4. Future research recommendation - to ensure proper and effective of the learning delivery modality, the following topics are recommended for future research:
 - a) Learning Delivery Modality in the New Normal
 - b) Performance of College Students in Implementing Hyflex Learning

c) Lived Experiences of Teachers in Implementing Hyflex Learning

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